

Optimizing Laser-Wakefield accelerator performance by varying gas density profiles using PIC codes

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Abstract

English:

Laser-wakefield accelerators, providing high-energy electrons on a small scale, are promising alternatives to conventional particle accelerators. High field gradients in the regime of several $\frac{\text{GeV}}{\text{m}}$ grant significant energy gain already in the range of millimeters and therefore table-top applications of LWFA are feasible.

Nevertheless, improving the beam quality is essential for future applications. With the development of particle-in-cell (PIC) algorithms, a time resolved analysis of plasma based accelerators became available, providing a steady optimisation potential of the electron beam. Using the PIC code PIconGPU, the influence of a density down-ramp on the characteristic Courant-Snyder parameters and the evolution fundamental beam properties is presented in this work. Through the visualisation of these quantities on the millimetre scale of the plasma, the oscillation of the beam parameters and the expansion of the beam waist in the down-ramp region can be demonstrated and furthermore, the average energy and total amount of charge in the main electron bunch is determined at the end of each plasma stage.

Thus, a detailed discussion of the down-ramp influence on the Courant-Snyder parameters, the bunch-charge and the beam energy, is provided for every simulation. Comparing the results with a reference simulation reveals optimisation possibilities of all mentioned parameters.

It is shown, that a perfectly matched beam is not yet reached for the assumed setup, but still an optimal density profile, combining low beam divergence and high energy and bunch charge, is suggested in the end of this work.

Deutsch:

Laser-Wakefield Beschleuniger sind eine kompakte und vielversprechende Alternative zu klassischen Teilchenbeschleunigern. Durch hohe Feldgradienten im Bereich von einigen $\frac{\text{GeV}}{\text{m}}$ wird eine starke Beschleunigung im Millimeterbereich erreicht, wodurch eine sehr breite Einsatzmöglichkeit der Laser-Wakefield Beschleuniger ermöglicht wird.

Für weitreichende Anwendungsmöglichkeiten ist es dennoch essenziell die Qualität des Elektronenstrahls zu verbessern. Durch die Entwicklung von „particle-in-cell“ (PIC) Algorithmen ist die Möglichkeit geboten, die zeitliche Entwicklung des Elektronenstrahls im Plasma nachzuvollziehen und der Einfluss einzelner Parameter hinsichtlich einer Strahloptimierung zu untersuchen. In dieser Arbeit wird der Einfluss eines abfallenden Dichteprofiles auf die Courant-Snyder Parameter und die fundamentalen Eigenschaften des Elektronenstrahls mithilfe von „PIConGPU“ untersucht.

Visualisierungen der entsprechenden Parameter auf der Längenskala des Plasmas zeigen das oszillierende Verhalten der Strahlparameter sowie das Anwachsen der Strahlbreite im Bereich abfallender Dichte. Zudem werden die mittlere Energie und die Gesamtladung des Strahls am Ende von jeder Simulation bestimmt.

Der Einfluss des Dichteprofiles auf die Courant-Snyder Parameter, die Strahlenergie und die Gesamtladung wird damit detailliert diskutiert und die Optimierungsmöglichkeiten jener Parameter durch einen Vergleich mit der Referenzsimulation dargelegt.

Für die untersuchte Konfiguration wurde ein perfektes „Matching“ nie vor dem abfallenden Dichteprofil erreicht. Dennoch kann am Ende ein optimales Dichteprofil vorgeschlagen werden, welches eine kleine Divergenz bei gleichzeitig hoher Energie und Ladung erlaubt.

Table of Contents

Abstract	iii
1 Laser Wakefield Acceleration	3
1.1 Laser Interaction with Atoms	3
1.1.1 Multi-Photon Ionisation (MPI)	3
1.1.2 Tunnelling and Over-The-Barrier Ionisation	5
1.2 Laser Interaction with Electrons - The Ponderomotive Force	6
1.3 Short Pulse Lasers in Underdense Plasmas	7
1.3.1 The Ponderomotive Force in a Plasma	8
1.3.2 The Electric Field and Electron Distribution Inside the Plasma	9
1.3.3 The Blowout Regime	10
1.3.4 Reaching the Blowout Regime with Plasma Self Focusing	11
1.4 Particle Injection Into the Wakefield	13
1.4.1 Spontaneous Injection	13
1.4.2 Down-Ramp Injection	14
1.4.3 Ionisation Injection	14
1.5 Limitations to Ideal Particle Acceleration in a Plasma	15
1.5.1 Dephasing Limit of Wakefield Acceleration	15
1.5.2 Depletion of the Driver Laser	15
1.5.3 Beam Emittance and Divergence	17
2 Optimisation of the Beam Quality	21
2.1 Discussion on Dephasing and Depletion Length of a Plasma Stage	21
2.2 Minimising the Beam Divergence at a Plasma-Vacuum Transition with a Density Down-Ramp	22
3 Modelling Laser Wakefield Acceleration with Particle-in-Cell Codes	25
3.1 The PIC Algorithm	25
3.1.1 A: Calculate Forces	25
3.1.2 B: Motion of Particles	26
3.1.3 C: Evaluate Current	26
3.1.4 D: Evolution of Fields	27
3.2 Data Analysis with the OpenPMD Standard	27

4	PIC Simulations of Down-Ramp Density Profiles	29
4.1	Fundamental Setup of the Simulations	29
4.1.1	Laser Parameters	29
4.1.2	Composition and Structure of the Plasma	30
4.2	Reference Simulation - Double Gaussian Profile	31
4.2.1	Energy Histograms for the Reference Simulation	31
4.2.2	Courant-Snyder Parameters of the Reference Simulation	35
4.3	Influence of the Down-Ramp	36
4.3.1	Energy Distribution at the End of the Matching Section	36
4.3.2	The Evolution of the Beam Quality	39
5	Conclusion	45
6	Outlook	49
	Bibliography	51

Introduction

For the past couple of decades, improving the acceleration of (charged) particles has been of major concern for novel physical research. Well known experiments, such as the discovery of the Higgs-Boson at LHC in 2012, or lately the muon $g-2$ experiment at Fermilab, were using high energy particle beams. In order to achieve the centre of mass energies of several GeV in collision experiments, particles have to gain high momenta. In case of the Fermilab Muon Storage Ring, muons of 3.1 GeV.[1]

Furthermore, accelerated particles can be useful for medical applications like radiation-therapy against tumours. Due to the characteristic energy loss spectra, ^{12}C -Beams of several MeV can be used for controlled radiation of cell tissue.[2]

Common particle accelerators are based on radio frequency cavities. But because of physical limitations like the vacuum breakdown, it is not possible to gain an arbitrary amount of energy per meter - linear electron accelerators like ELBE at the HZDR can reach electric field gradients of $10 \frac{\text{MeV}}{\text{m}}$ [3] - and therefore kilometre long tubes are necessary to gain energies in the GeV regime. Thus, ring accelerators are a practical implementation to reuse acceleration space. But due to synchrotron radiation the compactness of circular accelerators is also limited.

However, it is highly desirable to minimise the size of particle accelerators, leading to decreasing personnel and material costs and increasing possibilities of application.

Unlike conventional accelerators, Laser Wakefield Accelerators (LWFA) do not obey the limitation of the energy gradient inside the acceleration cavities. They can reach up to several $100 \frac{\text{GeV}}{\text{m}}$ [4] and can be build much smaller accordingly. Additionally, shorter bunch length and higher charge is reached inside the cavities, leading to currents of tens of kiloampere, whereas radio frequency cavities only reach a few kiloamperes [5]. The performance of Laser Plasma Accelerators is quantified experimentally by the acceleration of a few pC of charge to a few GeV [6, 7], which is mostly limited to dephasing and depletion limits. It has recently been shown theoretically, that energies of several GeV up to TeV becomes imaginable in LWFA [8]. Furthermore, the dispersion of the electron bunch is another limiting factor to the beam quality. They typically show a large energy spread and divergences of several milliradians [9], which can be controlled by focusing forces inside the plasma but not outside. It was therefore proposed to properly taper a down-ramp plasma density at the end of the plasma stage to minimise the divergence.

This idea will be further elaborated for the case of self-injected electrons in the following

sections. Therefore, different density down-ramps are modeled with PIC simulations and the energy distribution is investigated. In particular, the average beam energy and bunch charge will be analysed with energy histograms of the injected electrons. Moreover, a detailed analysis of the Courant-Snyder parameters for each down-ramp simulation provides an understanding of the beam quality for every timestep of the PIC simulation.

It is pointed out in the end, that the presence and also the shape of a down-ramp essentially influences the beam properties and an optimisation can be reached for setups similar to those realised in experiments at HZDR.

1 Laser Wakefield Acceleration

1.1 Laser Interaction with Atoms

A simple model of an atom in its ground state is given by a Coulomb potential $\Phi_{\text{coulomb}} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q}{r}$. Replacing $r = a_B$ with the Bohr radius $a_B = 5.3 \times 10^{-11}$ m and $E(r) = \frac{d\Phi}{dr}$, the electric field strength results in

$$E_{\text{atom}} = \frac{Q}{4\pi\epsilon_0 a_B^2} \approx 5.1 \times 10^{-9} \frac{\text{V}}{\text{m}}. \quad (1.1)$$

For the example of a hydrogen atom in its ground state Φ_{coulomb} presents a pretty good approximation of the atomic potential.

A single electron in such a potential can be considered as free, for $r \rightarrow \infty$. Accordingly, the ionisation energy can be found by integrating the electric field strength over (a_B, ∞) and multiplying with the elementary charge. This results in:

$$I_{\text{ion}} = \frac{Q^2}{8\pi\epsilon_0 a_B} \approx 13.6 \text{ eV} \quad (1.2)$$

in accordance with the energy of the ground state electron in the hydrogen atom.

For the interaction of an atom with an incoming laser pulse, it is necessary to investigate the scattering of photons on the electrons in the atomic shell. If the condition $E_\gamma > I_{\text{ion}}$ (with photon energy E_γ) holds true, the electron gains enough energy to escape the Coulomb potential and remains with kinetic energy $E_{\text{kin}} = I_{\text{ion}} - E_\gamma$. This ionisation process is shown in figure 1.1. If above's relation is not satisfied, a single photon ionisation does not occur. Instead, the atom adopts a virtual excited state of a short lifespan, where the bounded electron absorbs the photon and adopts an additional energy of $E_{\text{exc}} = E_0 + E_\gamma$.

1.1.1 Multi-Photon Ionisation (MPI)

If the photon energy is smaller than the ionisation energy, the energy of multiple photons can be combined in order to reach enough energy to remove the electrons from the atomic potential. Assuming the depletion time of the excited atom to be long enough for additional interactions with photons, the energy of the shell electron increases by the factor E_γ with each photon interaction (as in figure 1.2).

Figure 1.1: Qualitative Coulomb potential of a hydrogen atom. The electron (represented by the square of the quantum mechanical wave function) escapes the potential if the excitation energy $E_{exc} = E_0 + E_\gamma > 0$.

A simple expression for the multi-photon ionisation rate is given by [10]:

$$\Gamma_n = \sigma_n I_n^\gamma \quad (1.3)$$

where n represents the number of photon-electron interactions. According to the laws of fundamental quantum electrodynamic particle physics, the cross section σ_n of multi photon-electron scattering is suppressed by a factor $\propto \alpha^n$ with α being the fine structure constant. On the other hand, the intensity of the photon current I_n^γ increases.

This makes multi-photon ionisation possible for comparably low laser intensities of $I_{laser} > 10^{10} \frac{W}{cm^2}$ [10]. After the last ionisation, the electrons remain with a kinetic energy of $E_{kin} = nE_{photon} - E_{ion}$.

Figure 1.2: Qualitative Coulomb potential of an hydrogen atom. The electron (represented by the quantum mechanical wave function) escapes the potential if the excitation energy $E_{exc} = E_0 + n \cdot E_\gamma > 0$.

1.1.2 Tunnelling and Over-The-Barrier Ionisation

Another possibility for an ionisation process can be found by modifying the atomic potential instead of increasing the (multi-)photon energy. The atomic potential follows a r^{-1} behaviour as in figure 1.1 and can be readily modified by applying an external electric field. A simple, linear electrostatic potential is given by $V_{\text{mod}} = -Q\epsilon r$ with field strength parameter ϵ . Additionally applying such a potential to V_{coulomb} yields:

$$V(r) = V_{\text{coulomb}} + V_{\text{mod}} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{ZQ^2}{r} - Q\epsilon r. \quad (1.4)$$

The modified potential can be seen in figure 1.3.

It can be seen, that the potential becomes smaller than the binding energy (E_b) of the electron for $x \gg x_{\text{max}}$, which enables tunnelling effects through this potential barrier. For increasing field strength ϵ , $V(x_{\text{max}})$ may even fall below the binding energy and the electrons escape the potential. This so called over-the-barrier ionisation (OBI) occurs for the critical field strength $\epsilon_{\text{crit}} \geq \frac{E_b^2}{4ZQ^3}$ [10].

If the period of a laser $T = \frac{2\pi}{f}$ is large compared to the duration of interatomic processes and can be assumed constant of the time scale of the ionisation, the barrier suppression may also be caused by a laser pulse of specific intensity. In case of an hydrogen atom, the binding energy $E_b = 13.61 \text{ eV}$ leads to $\epsilon_{\text{crit}} = 0.32 \times 10^9 \frac{\text{V}}{\text{m}}$. Now the appearance intensity for OBI follows through evaluation of the peak electric field of the laser [10]:

$$I_{\text{app}} = \frac{c}{8\pi} \epsilon_{\text{crit}}^2 \quad (1.5)$$

$$\Rightarrow I_{\text{app}}(H) = 1.4 \times 10^{14} \frac{\text{W}}{\text{cm}^2} \quad (1.6)$$

which can be achieved with modern laser technology [11].

Figure 1.3: The qualitative Coulomb potential has been modified with a linear potential V_{mod} e.g. from a laser pulse. The height of the potential barrier decreases with increasing strength of the disturbing potential. Quantum mechanically the probability that the electron tunnels through the potential increases. If the barrier falls below the ground state energy E_0 , the electron escapes the potential.

1.2 Laser Interaction with Electrons - The Ponderomotive Force

For the moment, we assume a single electron under the influence of a Gaussian laser pulse, which can be described by the wave vector $A_0 = a_0 \cos \phi$ multiplied with a temporal envelope $f(t)$, where a_0 is the normalised amplitude of the electric field and $\phi = \omega t - \vec{k}\vec{r}$ the phase with wave vector \vec{k} and circular frequency ω .

The movement of electrons in an electromagnetic field can be described according to the Lorentz Equation,

$$\frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} = -e \left(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B} \right) \quad (1.7)$$

together with a relativistic energy equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\gamma mc^2) = -e(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{E}) \quad (1.8)$$

where $\vec{p} = m\gamma\vec{v}$ and $\gamma = \sqrt{1 + \frac{p^2}{(mc)^2}}$ [10].

Assuming a circular polarised laser pulse moving in x-direction, the wave vector can be written in particular as $\vec{A} = (0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_0 \cos \phi, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_0 \sin \phi)$.

It can be shown, that

$$\vec{p}_T = \vec{A} + \vec{p}_{T,0} \quad (1.9)$$

describes the transverse momentum of the electrons in the field of such a laser pulse. And furthermore a relationship between transverse and longitudinal momentum can be found:

$$p_l = \frac{1}{2k}(1 - k^2 + p_T^2). \quad (1.10)$$

A detailed derivation of (1.9) and (1.10) can be found in [10].

The arbitrary constant k can be determined by the choice of reference frame. Assuming the laboratory frame, where the electron initially rests ($\vec{p}_0 = 0$) it follows from (1.10) that $k = 1$. Furthermore, (1.9) suggests, that the transverse momentum equals the vector potential of the electromagnetic wave, which leads to the following expression for all three momenta:

$$p_x = \frac{(a_0 f(t))^2}{4} \quad (1.11)$$

$$p_y = \frac{a_0 f(t)}{\sqrt{2}} \cos(\omega t - k\vec{r}) \quad (1.12)$$

$$p_z = \frac{a_0 f(t)}{\sqrt{2}} \sin(\omega t - k\vec{r}) \quad (1.13)$$

Straightforward integration of equations (1.11) - (1.13) finally leads to the following expressions

[10]:

$$x = \frac{(a_0 f(t))^2}{4} (\omega t - k\vec{r}) \quad (1.14)$$

$$y = \frac{a_0 f(t)}{\sqrt{2}} \sin(\omega t - k\vec{r}) \quad (1.15)$$

$$z = -\frac{a_0 f(t)}{\sqrt{2}} \cos(\omega t - k\vec{r}). \quad (1.16)$$

From above equations several characteristics of laser-electron interactions can be seen, which will also be important for the case of a plasma in chapter 1.3. First of all, the electron starts to drift with an average drift momentum $p_{drift} = p_x = \frac{(a_0 f(t))^2}{4}$, strongly depending on the normalised amplitude of the e.-m. wave.

For $a_0 \ll 1$ the longitudinal motion of the electron can be neglected and the transverse momentum dominates. Accordingly, the longitudinal position of the electrons remains almost unchanged, while the transverse position oscillates around the beam axis with a radius $\frac{a_0}{\sqrt{2}}$. After the pulse has passed, all three momenta are zero and the electrons returns to rest.

For relativistic field strength ($a_0 \gg 1$), the electrons gain an additional momentum \vec{p} with longitudinal and transverse component. Through some relativistic kinematics, the relation between longitudinal and tangential drift can be derived and is explicitly shown in [10]:

$$p_{long} = \frac{p_{trans}^2}{2mc}. \quad (1.17)$$

Hence, the electron is ejected from its original position with momentum \vec{p} at an angle

$$\theta = \arctan \frac{\vec{p}_{trans}}{\vec{p}_{long}} \quad (1.18)$$

and oscillates around this vector. After the pulse has passed, the oscillation stops and the single electron moves with momentum \vec{p} [10].

1.3 Short Pulse Lasers in Underdense Plasmas

This chapter will be devoted to the investigation of laser-plasma interaction.

Considering a laser pulse with a Gaussian-like envelope, the electrons in the plasma see an electromagnetic field $E(r)$ of radial dependency. Electrons close to the beam centre feel stronger field gradients than those at the edge of the pulse. Thus, the transverse velocity of the plasma electrons

$$v(r, t) = \frac{eE_0(r)}{m\omega_0} \cdot \cos \omega t \quad (1.19)$$

depends on the distance to the beam axis, leading to interesting refractive properties of the plasma.

This effect is fundamental for the physics of laser propagation in a plasma and will be discussed later in section 1.3.4

1.3.1 The Ponderomotive Force in a Plasma

In the previous sections, the interaction of a laser with single atoms and electrons has been discussed. These results are now used to understand the laser-plasma interactions and to explain how a laser pulse drives a plasma wake.

Unlike in the single-electron case, the electromagnetic wave is now passing through a medium (in this case a plasma). Accordingly the dispersion relation is now given by

$$\omega^2 = \omega_{\text{plasma}}^2 + c^2 k^2 \quad (1.20)$$

with plasma frequency $\omega_{\text{plasma}} = \sqrt{\frac{n_e q^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e}}$ [5].

In section 1.2 it has been shown that free electrons are pushed to the edge of a laser pulse envelope and gain a longitudinal momentum proportional to the square of the normalised field strength due to the ponderomotive force of the electromagnetic wave. In the case of non relativistic intensities, an analytical expression of this force is given by

$$\vec{F}_{\text{pond}} = -\frac{q^2}{4m_e \omega_0^2} \vec{\nabla} \hat{E}^2 \quad (1.21)$$

with laser frequency ω_0 and envelope \hat{E}^2 [12]. A relativistic version of this formula becomes more complex to determine and “ is still a field of ongoing research ” [5]. A far from rigorous expression is given by

$$\vec{F}_{\text{pond}} = -m c^2 \vec{\nabla} \left\langle \left(1 + \frac{\vec{p}_{d,\text{slow}}^2}{m^2 c^2} + \frac{a_0^2}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\rangle \quad (1.22)$$

containing only the slow component of the drift momentum \vec{p}_d and averaging over a laser cycle [10].

Nevertheless the qualitative result remains the same in both cases. The laser pulse moves through the plasma like a snowplow through the snow, pushing electrons away from areas of high intensity and exciting a plasma wave with phase velocity equal to the lasers group velocity [13].

$$v_p^{\text{plasma}} = v_g^{\text{laser}} = c \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_{\text{plasma}}^2}{\omega_0^2}} \quad (1.23)$$

Due to the ponderomotive force, charges are separated in the plasma, which causes the occurrence of a positively charged plasma cavity behind the laser pulse. Electrons that gained were pushed aside by the laser pulse subsequently feel an attracting potential and start oscillating around the beam axis.

In case of non relativistic intensities ($a_0 < 1$) the plasma response is linear and the laser pulse excites a spherical cavity. For higher intensities relativistic effects become important, causing a rather non-linear response of the plasma [5]. The spherical shape of the cavity is not changed for increasing field strength, but it will be seen in 1.3.2, that the density distribution and thus the electromagnetic fields are changed due to relativistic effects.

1.3.2 The Electric Field and Electron Distribution Inside the Plasma

The impact of the ponderomotive force can be modelled by a potential Φ , which can be described by a second order differential equation

$$\Psi(\xi) = \frac{q_e \phi}{m_e c^2} \quad (1.24)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial \xi^2} = k_p^2 \gamma_p^2 \left[\beta_p \left(1 - \frac{1 + a^2(\xi)}{\gamma_p^2 (1 + \Psi(\xi))} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right] \quad (1.25)$$

where $\xi = x - ct$ represents the co-moving position, $k_p = \frac{\omega_{\text{plasma}}}{c}$ the plasma wave number and $a(\xi)$ the normalised plasma envelope in units of a_0 [5]. Again, $\beta_p = \frac{v_p}{c}$ and $\gamma_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta_p^2}}$ are the common relativistic factors. From the solution of this potential an analytical expression for the longitudinal electric field and the electron density can be found. A detailed derivation of the following expressions can be found in [10]:

$$\frac{E_{\text{long}}}{E_0} = -\frac{c}{\omega_{\text{plasma}}} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} \quad (1.26)$$

$$\frac{n_e}{n_0} = \gamma_p^2 \beta_p \left[\left(1 - \frac{1 + a^2(\xi)}{\gamma_p^2 (1 + \Psi(\xi))} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \beta_p \right] \quad (1.27)$$

with the initial plasma density n_0 and wave breaking field $E_0 = \frac{m_e c \omega_{\text{plasma}}}{q_e}$ introduced by Tajima and Dawson [13].

For the longitudinal electric field, the maximal reachable field strength is given by [14]

$$E_{\text{long}}^{\text{max}} = \frac{m_e c \omega_{\text{plasma}}}{q_e}. \quad (1.28)$$

As shown in section 1.2 the electron response to the ponderomotive force strongly depends on the field strength a_0 . In the case of non relativistic intensities ($a_0 \leq 0.5$) the response is linear and the plasma density and longitudinal field are sinus shaped. The oscillating electron distribution induces a $\frac{\pi}{2}$ -shifted electric field (relative to n_e) with the same wavelength, which switches its signum at the local extremes of the density distribution.

This is also the case for mid-relativistic energies ($a_0 \approx 1.5$), but the plasma response becomes nonlinear in this case. The electron density is rather peak-shaped, generating a sawtooth like electric field [14]. Both cases are illustrated in figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Visualisation of a plasma (with density $n_0 = 1 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) response to a laser pulse with pulse duration $\tau = 15 \text{ fs}$. The first plot illustrates the linear response to a laser pulse in the non-relativistic regime ($a_0 = 0.5$). In the second plot the non-linear response to a mid-relativistic laser pulse ($a_0 = 1.5$) is shown.

The laser pulse at co-moving position $\xi = 0$ generates the characteristic distribution of electron density $\frac{n_e}{n_0} - 1$ (black), longitudinal electric field $\frac{E_z}{E_0}$ (orange) and potential Φ (blue-dotted). *Source:* [5]

Electrons can be accelerated over half of a period of the longitudinal field, from areas of high density to regions of lower density. Once an electron is trapped in such a cavity, it will follow the laser pulse and gain significant energy until it runs into the decelerating region [15].

A 3D visualisation of a plasma wake can be seen in figure 1.5. Plasma electrons are pushed aside by the laser pulse and start oscillating around the beam axis, building a cavity, which is completely electron free in this case. This special case will be discussed in detail in the next section 1.3.3.

1.3.3 The Blowout Regime

If all electrons are pushed to the side by the ponderomotive force, a totally electron free cavity, a so called blowout regime, can be produced [15]. Optimal conditions for a blowout regime are reached with laser intensities of at least $a_0 > 4$ [5].

This leads to extremely strong accelerating and focusing fields, providing optimal conditions for high beam qualities. An optimal blowout regime is reached if the cavity has spherical shape, with radius $R = \lambda_{\text{plasma}}$ and the laser spot size matches this radius [5]. Under these conditions the maximal reachable strength of the longitudinal field increases by a factor of $\sqrt{a_0}$ compared to (1.28) [5].

Figure 1.5: Visualisation of a three dimensional blowout regime. The ponderomotive force of the laser pulse (red-blue) generates an electron free plasma cavity and the electron bunch can be accelerated. *Source:*[5]

In the co-moving position of the cavity centre, the longitudinal and transverse fields are described by:

$$E_{\text{long}}(\xi) = \frac{1}{2}k_{\text{plasma}} \cdot \xi \cdot E_0 \quad (1.29)$$

$$E_{\text{trans}}(r) \approx \frac{1}{4}k_{\text{plasma}} \cdot r \cdot E_0 \quad (1.30)$$

$$B_{\text{trans}}(r) \approx -\frac{1}{4} \frac{k_{\text{plasma}} \cdot r}{c} \cdot E_0 \quad (1.31)$$

with ξ and E_0 as in section 1.3.2 [5].

The radial dependency of (1.30) and (1.31) forces of axis electrons back to the centre of the cavity. These electrons start to oscillate around the beam axis at betatron frequency, emitting x-ray radiation [16]. In 1.6 such an electron free cavity is visualised for the two-dimensional case.

The large density increase at the back of the bubble is characteristic for the blowout regime [5] and can be useful for the injection of electrons into the bubble (see section 1.4).

1.3.4 Reaching the Blowout Regime with Plasma Self Focusing

The focal position, defined as the point of minimal beam waist w_0 , is a characteristic parameter of a laser pulse. Here, the beam waist is given as the distance from the beam axis where the intensity decreased to the $\frac{1}{2}$ -th part.

In case of vacuum conditions, the transverse spot radius increases by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ after the characteristic Rayleigh length [5]

$$L_{\text{rayleigh}} = \frac{\pi w_0^2}{\lambda_0} \quad (1.32)$$

Figure 1.6: Visualisation of a plasma (with density $n_0 = 1 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) response to a laser pulse with pulse duration $\tau = 15 \text{ fs}$. The upper plot visualises the electron distribution $\frac{n_e}{n_0}$ (black), laser field $\frac{E_{\text{laser}}}{a_0}$ and transverse focusing force F_r in a two dimensional histogram. It can be seen, that the laser pushes away all electrons and a *blowout regime* occurs. In a second plot the distribution of electron density $\frac{n_e}{n_0} - 1$ (black), longitudinal electric field $\frac{E_z}{E_0}$ (orange) and potential Φ (blue-dotted) can be seen. The plasma response becomes highly non-linear for the normalised field strength $a_0 = 5.0$. *Source:* [5]

after the focus. Thus, after the length L_{rayleigh} the transverse area of the pulse has doubled and the normalised laser intensity halved.

Adding a plasma to this setup changes the propagation of the laser pulse. The dispersion relation of the electromagnetic wave depends on the refractive index of the plasma, which is influenced by the electron density. An approximate expression for the refractive index (normalised to c) is given by:

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{\omega_{\text{plasma}}^2}{2\omega_0^2} \left(1 + \frac{\Delta n_{\text{channel}}}{n_0} \frac{r^2}{\omega_0^2} + \frac{\Delta n}{n_0} - \frac{a_0^2}{8} \right) \quad (1.33)$$

where $\frac{\Delta n_{\text{channel}}}{n_0}$ represents a density gradient for a preformed plasma channel and $\frac{\Delta n}{n_0}$ some density fluctuations [17].

Due to the ponderomotive force, the plasma electrons accumulate around the laser pulse envelope and especially in front of the laser pulse. Accordingly, the refractive index should be maximal directly on the beam axis ahead of the laser pulse. Equation (1.33) contains a term with radial dependency, confirming the decrease of the refractive index with increasing distance to the beam axis.

The off-axis phase velocity is therefore higher than on axis, which leads to a self focusing effect of the laser pulse. Because of that, a laser pulse inside a plasma stage can propagate over several Rayleigh lengths, without losing focus. And furthermore, the spot size can decrease due to this self focusing effect. As the laser intensity increases with smaller spot sizes, a blowout

regime can be reached with a laser pulse in the mid-relativistic regime ($2 \leq a_0 \leq 4$) as well. A time dependant development of the normalised intensity and the spot size can be seen in figure 1.7. For comparison, the vacuum evolution is visualised by a dashed line.

Figure 1.7: Evolution of the laser spot size and field strength. The blue area represents a region where the influence of self focusing is observable. Accordingly, the laser spot size w_0 (green-solid) decreases during the propagation through the plasma, leading to increasing field strengths a_0 (orange-solid). The vacuum evolution of the appropriate quantity is shown in dotted lines of the same colour. *Source:*[5]

1.4 Particle Injection Into the Wakefield

In the previous sections, the generation of a plasma wake and the corresponding electric fields have been discussed. From this theoretical background, it is now the aim to discuss the ability to accelerate charged particles, using such a plasma wakefield.

First of all, it is shown how electrons can be injected into the plasma cavity, and how they are trapped inside of the wakefield. Therefore, the spontaneous injection, the down-ramp injection and the ionisation injection are discussed for the blowout regime in this chapter.

It has already been shown by (1.27) and in figure 1.4 that the density becomes very high in regions, at the end of a plasma cavity. The physical properties of such a region are crucial for the *spontaneous-* and *down-ramp injection*.

1.4.1 Spontaneous Injection

Figure 1.4 indicates, that the longitudinal electric field is zero in the centre of a density peak. A large number of electrons accumulates in such a region and fluctuations may cause a spontaneous injection of several electrons into the cavity [5]. Once the electrons left this region, they feel an accelerating force generated by the cavity itself. Furthermore, the tangential field

components also force them to stay on the beam axis and follow the laser pulse [5].

This self injection occurs intrinsic and at normalised intensities of $a_0 > 4$ [18], accordingly it is experimentally easy to achieve. Unfortunately the injection relies on the cavity development and is therefore not necessarily stable in experiments.

Due to statistical effects like particle fluctuations, for example the Draco Laser at HZDR, achieves optimal bunch parameters in one out of ten cases [5].

1.4.2 Down-Ramp Injection

A more controllable method of electron injection is the down-ramp injection. Electrons can be captured in the plasma cavity by locally damping the plasma density, which increases the radius of the cavity $r_{\text{cav}} \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_e}}$ [5]. Electrons at the end of the bubble suddenly underlie an accelerating field and a bunch of electrons can be trapped (as seen before).

Such an injection also occurs naturally at the plasma-vacuum transition due to the decreasing density in that region [5]. This method leads to an experimental stable and reproducible injection, but can only capture a limited amount of electrons as the length of the down-ramp and hence the injection time is finite. About 100 pC of charge can be captured with this method [19].

1.4.3 Ionisation Injection

The ionisation injection is a method for getting electrons into the bubble without using electrons from the cavity itself. The large difference between the ionisation potential for K- and L-shell electrons (e.g. in Nitrogen) allows strong bound electrons to "survive" a prepulse of low intensity. The light bound electrons will be ionised immediately when the laser pulse arrives and get pushed to the edge, due to the ponderomotive force.

On the other hand, the K-shell electrons - for example of Nitrogen - have an ionisation energy of $E_{\text{ion}}(N^{6+}) = 552 \text{ eV}$ and $E_{\text{ion}}(N^{7+}) = 667 \text{ eV}$ [20]. A complete ionisation of Nitrogen would therefore require a normalised field strength of $a_0 = 2.75$ at $\lambda_0 \approx 800 \text{ nm}$ [5].

Unlike the down-ramp injection, the injection time is not limited in this case. As long as the laser pulse has enough energy to ionise the K-shell electrons, charge will be inserted into the cavity, which on the other hand leads to a broad energy spectra [5]. Lowering the laser intensity may reduce the ionisation length of K-shell electrons and the energy distribution narrows if the acceleration time is large compared to the injection time [20].

Generally, three conditions have to be fulfilled to capture electrons with ionisation injection:

1. High laser intensity for the ionisation of K-shell electrons.
2. Enough longitudinal momentum of ionised electrons, to keep up with the plasma wake.
3. A focusing field, keeping electrons in the cavity and minimising transverse emittance.

A trapping condition is given by

$$\Delta\Psi = \Psi_f - \Psi_i \lesssim -1 \quad (1.34)$$

where Ψ_f is the normalised wake potential at the end of the cavity and Ψ_i at the point of ionisation [20]. An expression for the normalised wake potential is given by $\frac{e}{mc^2}\Psi = (\Phi + \beta_\phi A_z)$ with scalar- and vector potential Φ and $vecA$ of the el.-magn. wave travelling in z-direction.

1.5 Limitations to Ideal Particle Acceleration in a Plasma

For modern Laser Wakefield Accelerators two major limitations prevent them from reaching even higher energies. The dephasing length, defining the length at which an electron outruns the accelerating field of the cavity and the depletion length, which denotes the length scale for depletion of the driver laser pulse [8].

1.5.1 Dephasing Limit of Wakefield Acceleration

In the area of interest, the longitudinal field of the plasma wake is an oscillating wave with phase velocity v_p . It has been shown, that the phase velocity of the plasma approximately matches the group velocity of the laser driver (equation (1.23)) and is smaller than the speed of light. The electrons on the other hand are not limited to this velocity and may approach the speed of light with increasing acceleration time [14]. It was pointed out in section 1.3.2, that charged particles can be accelerated for half a period of the electric field. Else, if the phase of the electron slips by one half of this period, they approach the decelerating regions of the wakefield and do not gain further energy [15].

In case of relativistic intensities, the dephasing length is given by [8]:

$$L_d = \frac{4}{3}c \frac{\omega_0^2}{\omega_{\text{plasma}}^3} \sqrt{a_0} \quad (1.35)$$

This dephasing limit can be increased through local adjustments of the plasma density (see 2) and the depletion of the driver laser becomes the limiting factor for further acceleration.

1.5.2 Depletion of the Driver Laser

Without any transverse focusing forces, a focused laser pulse diverges after a certain propagation time. For vacuum propagation the transverse spot radius of the laser increases by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ after the characteristic Rayleigh length according to equation 1.32.

In the case of plasma propagation, the transverse defocussing can be minimised through intrinsic focusing fields. The ponderomotive force generates a radial dependency of the plasma

refraction index and leads to laser self-focusing. Accordingly, the increase of the beam waist is prevented.

Nevertheless, the laser constantly transfers electromagnetic energy into the plasma during the excitation of a wakefield. Hence, the laser pulse loses energy and depletes with increasing propagation time. The (pump) depletion length is given by

$$L_{\text{depl}} = \frac{\omega_0^2}{\omega_{\text{plasma}}^2} c\tau. \quad (1.36)$$

where τ denotes a length scale for the energy depletion of the driver laser [17].

Figure 1.8 visualises the previously mentioned process. With increasing propagation time a major part of the laser energy converts into the plasma wake and the pulse depletes. At this point, the cavity collapses no further acceleration occurs.

The problem of pump depletion can be solved by using multiple plasma stages. It is possible to guide the accelerated electron bundle into a new wakefield and achieve further acceleration [5]. But as the stage coupling requires perfect timing and the beam defocusses at the plasma-vacuum transition, it is experimentally difficult to use laser wakefield accelerators with multiple plasma stages. Hence, optimizing the single-stage acceleration is a major concern in the LWFA development [8].

Figure 1.8: Propagation of a laser pulse through a plasma stage. Each figure represents a $101.7 \times 129.3 \mu\text{m}$ frame of the plasma. The laser intensity is shown in orange and the electron density blue. **(a):** The laser pulse generates a circular shaped blowout regime with radius R . **(b) and (c):** electrons are injected into the plasma cavity and the beam waist of the driver laser increases. The intensity of the Laser pulse decreases (orange shading) and the cavity starts to loose its spherical shape. **(d):** The energy of the laser is almost completely transferred into the wakefield. At this stage the laser pulse cannot excite a plasma wake anymore and the cavity depletes. *Source:*[17]

1.5.3 Beam Emittance and Divergence

Particles that are injected to a plasma cavity are guided by longitudinal- and transverse fields and oscillate around a so called equilibrium trajectory, given by the beam axis of the laser pulse. In the co-moving frame of the accelerated particle the transverse motion is given by Hills Differential Equation [21]

$$x'' + K(z)x = 0 \quad (1.37)$$

where x is a transverse- and z the longitudinal component of motion and the factor $K(z)$ describes the focusing strength inside the cavity. In case of a monoenergetic bunch, dispersive effects are negligible and equation (1.37) is the same for the y -component [21].

Equation (1.37) has the shape of a harmonic oscillator with spatially dependant frequency. A solution for this problem is given by a set of parameters α, β, γ and μ , which determine the so called Twiss-Matrix. A detailed derivation can be found in [21].

The beam parameters α, β and γ where first introduced by Courant and Snyder in 1958 [22] and are given by:

$$\alpha = -\frac{\langle xx' \rangle}{\epsilon} \quad \beta = \frac{\langle x^2 \rangle}{\epsilon} \quad \gamma = \frac{\langle x'^2 \rangle}{\epsilon} \quad (1.38)$$

with $\epsilon = \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle \langle x'^2 \rangle - \langle x x' \rangle^2}$ being the transverse beam emittance and $x' = \frac{p_x}{p_z}$ the slope of the particle trajectory [23]. Parameter μ specifies the stability of the solution [21].

In general, the movement of an electron bunch in a LWFA stage can be described by a six dimensional phase-space with canonical coordinates p_x, p_y, p_z, x, y and z [24]. Instead of approaching such a difficult six-dimensional phase-space, the two orthogonal planes $x - x'$ and $y - y'$ are considered here. Again, the prime suffix indicates the slope of the particle trajectory in the corresponding direction. This so called trace-space connects the phase space with the beam parameters α, β and γ .

The trace-space area of an electron bunch is given by an ellipse, as in 1.9a. The discussion is equivalent for both transverse coordinates as no direction stands out [24], which is why only the $x - x'$ -plane is mentioned here.

Figure 1.9: Evolution of a phase-space ellipse for an electron bunch in different scenarios. The transverse position x and momentum p_x are shown in arbitrary units. (a): Phase space area of an electron bunch. (b): Phase space area after a free drift of the electron bunch in vacuum. The dashed lines visualise the time evolution of the ellipse, which is stretched due to the initial (transverse) momentum of the electrons. Though, the intersection points with the x axis remain the same as the momentum is not changed. (c): Phase space evolution of an electron bunch under the influence of a focusing force with no longitudinal dependency. The phase space ellipse starts to rotate due to the focusing force (grey arrows) while the phase space area is conserved (Liouville's Theorem).

Figure 1.9: (d): Phase space evolution of an electron bunch in a realistic plasma stage. Due to the energy distribution of the electrons and longitudinal dependency of the focusing force, different bunch slices (represented by different ellipses) oscillate at different frequency, resulting in a phase space mixing. Matching conditions are reached, if the phase space area inside of the limiting circle is filled homogeneously.

In case of a free drift, the momentum of all particles is conserved. Particles with $x' < 0$ move to the left and others with $x' > 0$ to the right. This elongates the phase-space area, leading to a picture as in figure 1.9b. Such a beam shows a large divergence and cannot be collimated over long distance.

For LWFA a transverse focusing field guides the electron bunch and influences the trace-space propagation. An electron bunch of finite bunch-length can be separated into bunch slices at different co-moving positions ξ of the wave. These bunch slices perform betatron oscillations of different frequency [23] and may have an energy discrepancy. Furthermore, focusing strength $K(z)$ is a function of the longitudinal position z [25], which is why electrons at different positions to oscillate at different frequencies if the plasma density n_e is not constant. This causes a phase space mixing as shown in figure 1.9d until a so-called matching condition is reached. This is equivalent to $\alpha = 0$, meaning that the phase space is filled homogeneously with trace space ellipses of different bunch slices [25]. The β and γ parameters oscillate until the matching condition is fulfilled and remain constant when $\alpha = 0$. A schematic evolution of all three parameters can be seen in figure 1.10. In this case, the phase space mixing is explicitly caused by the energy difference of the bunch slices, as $\forall z : K(z) = \text{const.}$ for the given density profile.

At the end of a plasma channel the focusing field suddenly disappears and the beam continues to move in a free drift. Assuming a given setup, where the bunch is focused to a small spot size and shows large divergences right before the plasma-vacuum transition, the beam transport after the plasma stage becomes challenging [9].

For various applications, for example the coupling of multiple LWFA or PWFA stages, it is necessary to maintain the electron bunch in a free drift for some time [26]. It is therefore necessary to minimise the beam divergence x' and consequently the γ -parameter during the transition.

Figure 1.10: Evolution of the Courant Snyder parameters in a plasma stage without up- and down-ramp. The parameters are shown for three different cases: (CM): Matched case, (C1): Unmatched focal position and (C2): Unmatched beta function. *Source:* [23]

2 Optimisation of the Beam Quality

Optimising the beam quality of a plasma accelerated electron bunch is important to achieve a better applicability of LWFA. In general the acceleration process can be divided into three parts. The injection into the plasma (vacuum-plasma transition), which is relevant for external injection, the propagation through the plasma and the extraction from the plasma stage (plasma-vacuum transition).

It has already been shown by Dornmair and Floettmann [9] for the case of external injection, that locally tapering the focusing strength, namely at the entrance and exit of the plasma stage, optimises the beam quality and leads to the conservation of the phase-space emittances. Such a matching section between plasma and vacuum simplifies the beam dynamics after the plasma stage and allows the coupling into a magnetic beam transport system after the plasma stage for experimental purposes [26].

The propagation through the plasma stage will be discussed shortly in the following sections, but especially the influence of a plasma down ramp will be presented.

2.1 Discussion on Dephasing and Depletion Length of a Plasma Stage

It has been shown in section 1.5, that the dephasing and depletion length prevent LWFA stages from reaching bunch energies in the TeV regime. The dephasing length of the accelerated bunch is closely related to the plasma frequency $\sim \frac{1}{\omega_{\text{plasma}}^3}$. Locally damping the plasma density n_e would decrease the plasma frequency $\omega_{\text{plasma}} = \sqrt{\frac{n_e q^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e}}$ and increase the dephasing length [14]. The depletion length is proportional to $\sim \frac{1}{\omega_{\text{plasma}}^2}$. Similar to the dephasing problem, the pump depletion of the driver laser increases when the plasma density decreases. In [27] it has been shown, how a preformed plasma channel increases the propagation length of the laser and higher bunch energies can be reached.

Unfortunately, decreasing the electron density at constant laser intensities and acceleration time leads to a decreasing beam energy [17]. Accordingly, other parameters have to be tuned, if the beam energy should remain constant at lower plasma densities.

Another solution to the dephasing and depletion problem is proposed in [8]. The so called Travelling Wave Electron Acceleration uses a tilted pulse front, generated by two laser beams. It creates a hyperbolic cavity, moving with the velocity of light in vacuum, in front of the

electron bunch. Such a setup circumvents the usual dephasing and depletion limits for LWFA and higher energies may be reached.

2.2 Minimising the Beam Divergence at a Plasma-Vacuum Transition with a Density Down-Ramp

It has been shown in section 1.5.3, that an abrupt plasma-vacuum cut leads to a large beam spread after the plasma stage. But for various applications it is useful to minimise the beam divergence. It is therefore proposed to introduce a matching section at the end of a plasma stage [9], where the beam diameter is increased but simultaneously the transverse momentum decreased.

Equation (1.37) and especially the focusing strength $K(z)$ prescribes the transverse motion of the electron beam. If the matching condition for the beam is fulfilled and the betatron frequency changes adiabatically, the beam quality does not significantly reduce [23]. In other words, if the change of the focusing strength is slow compared to the phase advance, the beam is always matched and the phase-space emittance conserved [9].

If the focusing strength is reduced, the transverse beam diameter increases and hence, as the phase-space emittance is conserved, the beam divergence decreases [26].

The length of an adiabatic matching section is limited in realistic plasma stages, which leads to the question of an optimal tapering profile with minimal spacial expansion. In [25] numerical calculations of the beam emittance have been made for various field profiles with different tapering parameters. It was found that an expression for the optimal focusing strength is given by

$$K(z) = \frac{K_0}{(1 + gz)^4} \quad (2.1)$$

with initial focusing strength K_0 and taper parameter g [25].

Two parameters can be tuned in experiments, namely the beam waist $w(z)$ of the laser and the plasma density n_e , that influence the focusing strength inside of the cavity [9]. For the profile given by equation (2.1) the optimal laser spot at constant density is $w(z) = w_0(1 + gz)$ [9].

In the special case that a beam is at the dephasing point at the end of the accelerating process an approximate expression for the ideal density profile at constant $w(z)$ is

$$n(z) = n_0 (1 + agz + bg^2z^2)^{-2} \quad (2.2)$$

with $a \approx 3.45$ and $b \approx 1.59$ [9].

The simulations in this work use a density profile of the following shape in the matching

section:

$$n(z) = n_0 \cdot \exp(-gz) \quad (\text{with } z \geq 0). \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 2.1 presents a first illustration of a plasma stage with different down-ramp profiles. The second part visualises a plasma down-ramp according to equation (2.3) for three different taper parameters g , while a constant density is assumed for the first part.

Figure 2.1: The first part (red) represents a plasma of constant density up to a longitudinal position $y = 2.05$ mm. The green part visualises three different plasma down-ramps according to equation (2.3).

Compared to (2.2) the modeling of such a density profile is rather easy and 2.3 suits the experimental assumptions.

It is the aim of this work to find a taper parameter in equation 2.3 that optimises the beam divergence of the accelerated electrons through the adiabatic expansion of the electron bunch.

3 Modelling Laser Wakefield Acceleration with Particle-in-Cell Codes

In order to understand the behaviour of a whole plasma under the influence of a laser pulse, particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations are the method of choice for this work. For typical plasma densities of $n_e = \frac{10^{19}}{cm^3}$ one would have to track trillions of electrons already on a micrometer scale [5], leading to extraordinary computational challenges. PIC Algorithms overcome this problem with the introduction of macroparticles. These macroparticles merge a bunch of electrons located close to each other by treating their discrete charge as a continuous distribution around a central position on a mesh [28]. The PIC algorithm solves the Vlasov equation by sampling macroparticles with their associated momentum and weighting (number of real particles described by a macroparticle) for discrete time evolution in four steps [5, 29].

3.1 The PIC Algorithm

The PIC Algorithm is separated into four steps A-D, that are repeated for each iteration. Every step is discussed in the following sections and a schematic illustration of the „PIC-cycle “ is presented in figure 3.1.

3.1.1 A: Calculate Forces

For a given (macro-)particle distribution the algorithm interpolates the electric- and magnetic fields at the current position of the particles and determines the force at those points.

As long as no electromagnetic fields act on the plasma this step does not do anything. But through thermal motion, or with the injection of a laser pulse into the plasma, electric and magnetic fields influence the trajectory of the macroparticles, leading to step B.

Figure 3.1: Visualisation of the PIC-cycle. All of the steps are executed in a single iteration of the PIC code. *Source:*[5]

3.1.2 B: Motion of Particles

Electrons are moving according to Lorentz force $\vec{F}_l = q(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B})$. Numerically, the velocity and position of the particles can be calculated with a basic Euler method:

$$\vec{v} = \frac{\vec{F}_l}{m} = \frac{q(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B})}{m} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\vec{r}_{i+1} = \vec{r}_i + \Delta t \vec{v} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\vec{r}_{i+1} = \vec{r}_i + \Delta t \vec{v}_i. \quad (3.3)$$

But “the numerical error grows relatively fast with each time step”[5], which is why certain particle push algorithms are rather implemented in PIC algorithms. Beside the numerical stability, the computational requirements for these algorithm are not too challenging [5].

Once the updated position of the macroparticles is defined on the grid, the new electric and magnetic fields can be determined by either solving the Poisson equation or integrating Maxwell’s equations [10]. But for the integration of Maxwell, the electric current density has to be computed first.

3.1.3 C: Evaluate Current

It is numerically costly to solve the Poisson equation and most commonly, PIC algorithms determine a current density field \vec{J} to solve Amperes Law:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \vec{J} \right). \quad (3.4)$$

Evaluating the influence of the motion of macroparticles on discrete lattice points, the electric current can be resolved on the grid for every macroparticle. This results in a current density field \vec{J} .

3.1.4 D: Evolution of Fields

For each time step equation (3.4) and

$$\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = -\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} \quad (3.5)$$

can be solved numerically with the finite-difference-time-domain (FDTD) method introduced by Yee [30] and leads to the field evolution:

$$\vec{E}_{i+1} = \vec{E}_i + \Delta t \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B}_i - \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \vec{J} \right) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\vec{B}_{i+1} = \vec{B}_i - \Delta t \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E}_i \quad (3.7)$$

with discrete derivatives ∂_t for the time discretization and $\vec{\nabla}$ for the evolution on the grid [29].

3.2 Data Analysis with the OpenPMD Standard

The OpenPMD standard is a useful meta data format for the investigation of **particle** and **mesh based data**. Its main goal is to define a minimal set of metadata, that is readable to humans and readily accessible for automatic data analysis in scientific workflows.

OpenPMD simultaneously reads and writes the *heavy data*, e.g. from a PIC simulation, and stores them in *groups*. From the users point of view, the *records* are central objects of a certain *component* in a *group*. The *groups*, *subgroups* and array shaped *components* follow a strict hierarchy.

If an experimental data set, for example from a camera or a simulation, contains a minimal set of meta-data provided by OpenPMD, the exchange and processing of the data becomes very easy.

Additionally to the explicit value of a certain component, OpenPMD provides supplementary information as for example the `unit.SI` record. This allows OpenPMD to write components without scaling, to allow higher performance and make transformation into different unit systems, especially SI Units, possible.

4 PIC Simulations of Down-Ramp Density Profiles

4.1 Fundamental Setup of the Simulations

For an initial idea of the LWFA setup, some small scale simulations have been performed on k80-GPU's on the hemera cluster at HZDR. The influence of various parameters, e.g. laser amplitude, gas mixture, etc., was tested in these simulations. The results of these initial computer experiments have been used to develop a fundamental setup of a LWFA with a parameterised down-ramp profile (LWFA-DIC) for large scale PIC simulations on the Taurus cluster at the ZIH TU Dresden.

The only parameter that was changed in different simulations is the taper parameter of the down ramp density profile. All the other parameters remained untouched, thus the influence of different down-ramps can be investigated.

The most important laser and plasma parameters are discussed in the following and a first PIC simulation with these parameters is discussed.

4.1.1 Laser Parameters

The setup of the laser is selected in accordance with the DRACO at HZDR. The DRACO is a 150 Terawatt / Petawatt Ti:Saphir laser, producing high energy pulses with pulse lengths of 30 fs at wavelengths of 800 nm.

In the setup for LWFA-DIC simulations, a laser pulse of Gaussian shape and linear polarisation has been used. For such a pulse, the *pulse duration* is defined by the FWHM of the intensity and is set to $\tau \approx 12.74$ fs.

The laser wavelength is set to 800 nm, while the normalised amplitude of the laser is chosen in the mid relativistic regime: $a_0 \approx 2.65$. The amplitude a_0 can be converted into SI units by multiplication with a factor $k(\lambda)$:

$$\hat{E}_0 = a_0 \cdot k(\lambda) \tag{4.1}$$

$$= a_0 \cdot \frac{2\pi m_e c^2}{\lambda e} = 1.06 \times 10^{-13} \frac{\text{V}}{\text{m}}. \tag{4.2}$$

Furthermore, the focus position y_{focus} and the beam waist $w_0(y_{\text{focus}})$ can be tuned. The choice of the focus position for this setup has been investigated in simulations without a down-ramp

profile and is set to $y_{\text{focus}} = 1.5 \text{ mm}$ (relative to the beginning of the plasma density profile) with a beam waist $w_0(y_{\text{focus}}) = 17.4 \mu\text{m}$.

4.1.2 Composition and Structure of the Plasma

In general, three parameters define the internal structure of the plasma. The base density n_0 , the gas composition and the density profile $n(y)$. The influence of those quantities on the ionisation of the plasma (section 1.4.3), the wakefield generation (section 1.3.2) and also dephasing and depletion length (section 1.5) has been discussed in the previous chapters. Furthermore the influence of a density down-ramp on the beam divergence was discussed in section 2.2, which will be investigated in the following.

Models of realistic plasma stages (without up- and/or down-ramps) consist of a broad plateau of nearly constant density, that rapidly falls towards the edges of the channel. Therefore, a super Gaussian function:

$$n(y) = n_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(y - y_0)^4}{\sigma^4}\right) \quad (4.3)$$

as in figure 4.1 has been chosen as a primary profile.

For LWFA-DIC simulations, density profiles are separated into two parts. The first part includes the *vacuum-plasma-transition* and *plasma plateau* merging in the second part at y_{cutoff} , which defines the *plasma-vacuum-transition*. The shape of the down ramp profile will be discussed later in 4.3.

LWFA experiments operate with certain gas mixtures, containing either hydrogen or helium and doping atoms. For this setup a 99% helium 1% nitrogen mixture is chosen.

According to 1.4.3 a pre-pulse of low intensity ionises the five nitrogen L-shell and the two helium K-shell electrons. Therefore a pre-ionised initialisation of nitrogen and helium can be assumed for PIC simulations. Subsequently, the base density is given by

$$n_0 = 1.2 \cdot 10^{24} (N^{\text{He}} \cdot \varphi^{\text{He}} + N^{\text{N}} \cdot \varphi^{\text{N}}) \quad (4.4)$$

$$= 1.2 \cdot 10^{24} (2 \cdot 0.99 + 5 \cdot 0.01) \text{ m}^{-3} \quad (4.5)$$

where N^{X} is the amount of relatively light bound electrons in atom X and φ^{X} the volume fraction of this atom in the gas mixture.

Figure 4.1: Density profiles for LWFA-DIC simulations. The first part is defined by equation (4.3) with $y_0 = 1.6$ mm and $\sigma = 1.0$ mm and the down-ramp (second part) is discussed in section 4.3.

4.2 Reference Simulation - Double Gaussian Profile

This chapter provides a brief, illustrative introduction of the chosen method for the analysis of all simulations. With a first PIC simulation, the beam evolution without a density down-ramp is investigated. For this reference simulation, the properties of the accelerated electrons are demonstrated and the progression of all Courant-Snyder parameters is shown.

4.2.1 Energy Histograms for the Reference Simulation

In LWFA experiments two physical quantities are commonly measured in order to investigate the beam quality of the accelerated electron bunch. Namely, the energy E and the distribution of the moving angle $\theta = \arctan \frac{p_{\text{trans}}}{p_{\text{long}}}$. A favourable plasma stage generates many electrons with high energies (in the 100 MeV regime) with small transverse momentum.

In the upper part of figure 4.2 all electrons from the ionisation injection are visualised in a two dimensional histogram. The x-axis represents the energy of the electrons, while the y-axis corresponds to the associated angle of movement. In addition to the low E - large θ background, a density peak can be seen at $\theta \approx 0$ and average energy $\langle E \rangle = E_0 \approx 208$ MeV.

For the further analysis of that density peak a pure energy histogram of the same iteration is visualised in the lower part of 4.2. In this plot, a Gaussian fit function

$$Q(E) = Q_{\text{max}} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(E - E_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (4.6)$$

was applied and the following parameters were obtained:

$$E_0 = 208 \text{ MeV}, \quad Q_{\max} = 4.2 \text{ pC} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma = 14.3 \text{ MeV}.$$

Additionally the Full-Width-Half-Maximum of that Gaussian function can be derived:

$$\text{FWHM} = 2\sigma \cdot \sqrt{2 \ln 2} = 33.7 \text{ MeV}. \quad (4.7)$$

Figure 4.2: Two energy histograms representing electrons in the last PIC iteration of a double Gaussian density profile. The upper part illustrates the energy distribution of the injected electrons together with their moving angle in x-direction. In a second histogram the pure energy distribution of the same particles can be seen. A Gaussian fit function was applied to the energy histogram (second part) to obtain information about the energy peak.

The bunch charge Q^{bunch} is another interesting parameter of the respective setup and specifies the amount of electrons in the relevant region of the electron bunch. A quantification of Q^{bunch} is simply given by the summation of the electrons in the particular region. To prevent statistical errors in such a summation, for example through variation of the boundaries, the bunch charge is derived from the integration of the Gaussian fit function in the 2σ -range:

$$Q^{\text{bunch}} = \int_{-2\sigma}^{2\sigma} Q_{\max} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(E - E_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) dE \quad (4.8)$$

$$= 143.4 \text{ pC}. \quad (4.9)$$

This allows an adequate comparison between different simulations.

For an illustrative understanding of the acceleration- and adiabatic matching process, such a histogram can be generated for multiple time steps in PIC simulations.

All simulations run 180000 iterations, while writing OpenPMD data every 5000-th step. Ne-

glecting the initialisation where no (ionisation) injected electrons are produced, 36 data sets can be analysed. Presenting 36 histograms for every simulation would be way to much and non expedient, because only the down-ramp profile is changed in the simulations. The time evolution of the energy histograms is therefore shown for the reference simulation exceptionally and only the histograms of the last iteration are discussed for the down ramp simulations in section 4.3.

Figure 4.3 presents the evolution of the E - θ histogram at the given time steps. At the expense of information loss, especially in the first iterations, it was chosen to visualise the histograms series in figure 4.3 with a fixed x- and y-axis for all time steps. This presentation has the advantage that the energy gain as well as the transverse focusing of the electrons becomes readily visible in the upper plots.

The energy gain is also reproduced in the second plot of each iteration and additionally the amount of charge in that energy peak can be determined.

Because of the choice of a fixed energy axis, the analysis starts at $t = 3.3$ ps (4.3a) where a broad angle-distribution at comparably low energies can be seen. With further propagation of the driver laser the angle distribution is almost unchanged for slow electrons, but an increasing amount of electrons gain significant kinetic energy (4.3b) and a first glance of a density peak can be seen in 4.3c. The amount of electrons in that energy peak clearly increases in the following (4.3d) and after $t = 8.0$ ps the accelerated beam reached an average energy $\langle E \rangle \approx 208$ MeV (4.3e). In the following, the beam energy remained almost constant and the bunch charge does not significantly change. At this time of propagation through the plasma, the beam has reached a longitudinal position $y \approx 2.4$ mm which is a region where the density decreases again (see figure 4.1). Hence, the acceleration process gradually ends and the shape of the high energy peak is approximately constant.

The last iteration at $t = 13.1$ ps has already been analysed in 4.2.

Figure 4.3: Energy histograms for the down-ramp simulations. In each figure, the upper part illustrates the energy distribution of the injected electrons together with their moving angle in x-direction. In a second histogram the pure energy distribution of the same particles can be seen. For the visualisation of the histograms the scaling of x- and y axis have been fixed. This allows an appropriate comparison between the iteration steps but swallows slow electrons. Thus, the first illustration (a) starts at $t = 3.3$ ps. With increasing propagation time ((b)) it can be seen that some of the electrons gain kinetic Energy and simultaneously their transverse momentum decreases. Iteration (c), (d) and (e) illustrate how a first electron bunch is accelerated to ≈ 200 MeV and (f) illustrates both histograms for the last PIC iteration. The energy histogram in (f) has been fitted with a Gaussian fit function (4.6).

4.2.2 Courant-Snyder Parameters of the Reference Simulation

The investigation of the Courant-Snyder parameters $\alpha = -\frac{\langle xx' \rangle}{\epsilon}$, $\beta = \frac{\langle x^2 \rangle}{\epsilon}$ and $\gamma = \frac{\langle x'^2 \rangle}{\epsilon}$ provides a more detailed analysis of the beam dynamics and can be seen in figure 4.4. Each plot illustrates the respective parameter together with the density profile on a shared x-axis.

Figure 4.4: Evolution of the Courant-Snyder parameters for the reference density profile. Each figure illustrates the respective parameter together with the density profile on a shared x-axis (representing the longitudinal position).

Through the evolution of the alpha parameter, the oscillation of the electron bunch is explicitly visualised. Unfortunately, the relatively rough sampling of the longitudinal position absorbs information about the actual oscillation frequency and amplitude. But a fine sampling would require immense computational costs, due to increasing requirements concerning memory space and run-time, which would exceed the capabilities of this work.

Therefore, a rigorous discussion of the beam matching process is not possible within this thesis, but still the reaching of the matching condition can be observed. It can be seen for this simulation, that the oscillation continues in the area where the density decreases again and the alpha parameter is non zero at the end of the density plateau. It is therefore concluded that matching conditions are not reached at the end of the plasma channel.

The fact, that the beam is not matched to the plasma cavity at the end of the acceleration

process impacts the analysis of the down-ramp simulations as well.

It can be seen, that the spot size of the electron beam increases in an area, where the focusing strength is maximal. In accordance with Liouville's Theorem the gamma parameter continuously decreases in that region.

In the region of plasma-vacuum transition, the focusing strength decreases but a clear expansion of the beam together with a drastic minimisation of the beam divergence is not observed. It is seen, that the beam expands relatively fast if the plasma density is almost zero.

Because of the absence of focusing forces, a similar situation as in 1.9b (free-expansion) is found. Due to the transverse momentum of the electrons, the beam waist increases relatively fast and approximately doubles on the scale of micrometers.

4.3 Influence of the Down-Ramp

The influence of a down-ramp profile at the exit of a plasma stage has been tested in four different PIC simulations. Compared with the first simulation shown in section 4.2 only the density profile at the exit has been changed according to equation (2.3). For the transition from plateau to the adiabatic matching section a *cutoff position* y_{cutoff} can be defined. At this point the density changes from double Gaussian character to an exponential decay:

$$n(y) = \begin{cases} n_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(y-y_0)^4}{\sigma^4}\right) & y \leq y_{\text{cutoff}} \\ n_0 \cdot \exp(-g \cdot (y - y_{\text{cutoff}})) & y > y_{\text{cutoff}} \end{cases} \quad (4.10)$$

where g is the taper parameter.

The four LWFA-DIC simulations use the taper parameters g_1 - g_4 given by:

simulation	1	2	3	4
g/mm^{-1}	10	5.0	1.25	0.625

Table 4.1: Taper parameters of the four LWFA-DIC simulations.

4.3.1 Energy Distribution at the End of the Matching Section

Visualising the energy distribution as histograms (as in section 4.2) provides an initial comparison between all four down-ramp profiles. In figure 4.5 the energy-angle histograms together with a pure energy distribution can be seen.

All the histograms follow the qualitatively expected behaviour of a sharp angular distribution and an energy peak in the 100 MeV-regime. For the simulations with g_1 and g_2 the broad low-energy background is not observed, as the first few cells were ignored in the analysis of all histograms. In simulation 3 and 4 (4.5c and 4.5d), such a broad background is still recognised

for kinetic energies up to 50 MeV.

As these histograms only display those electrons that have been injected by ionisation injection into the plasma cavity, the low energy background represents those nitrogen K-shell electrons that were ionised from nitrogen later during the propagation of the laser. For simulations with small taper parameters (simulation 3 and 4) the injection process continues in the area of the plasma down-ramp. Tapering the plasma density in this area delays the defocussing of the driver laser and nitrogen atoms can still be ionised in down-ramp region. Furthermore, electrons that have been injected in this area experience weaker focusing forces than those in the plasma plateau. Hence, the θ -distribution remains smeared out also in the regime of higher energies.

Later in section 4.3.2 a more detailed analysis of the beam divergence, which is related to the moving angle θ , is discussed.

Figure 4.5: Energy histograms for the down-ramp simulations. In each figure, the upper part illustrates the energy distribution of the injected electrons together with their moving angle. In a second histogram the pure energy distribution of the same particles can be seen. Furthermore, an analysis of the high energy peak is provided, using a Gaussian fit function. (a): Histograms for taper parameter g_1 . Fit parameters can be found in 4.2.

The second part of the figures 4.5a-4.5d is considered for a comparison of the energy distribution of the electron bunches. Therefore, a fit of the main energy peak has been performed, using the same Gaussian fit function (4.6) as in section 4.2.

Table 4.2 summarises the fit parameters for all simulations together with the Full-Width-Half-

Maximum.

Simulation	$\frac{E_0}{MeV}$	$\frac{Q_{\max}}{pC}$	$\frac{\sigma}{MeV}$	$\frac{FWHM}{MeV}$
1	184	4.26	14.0	33.1
2	192	4.21	14.2	33.5
3	255	4.04	15.0	35.3
4	330	3.72	16.9	39.7

Table 4.2: Fit parameters for the Gaussian fit in the energy histogram for all simulations.

The influence of the down-ramp on the electron bunch can be seen in all parameters. But the most significant difference is the position of the energy peak. It is therefore already observed at this point, that the beam parameters and the bunch energy cannot be optimised simultaneously with the method of a density down-ramp.

For simulations with big g , the plasma density drastically falls after the cutoff length and the accelerating field strength decreases quickly. On the other hand, those fields remain strong for slowly falling down-ramps. Electrons in a plasma cavity are thus further accelerated in the down-ramp area and reach higher energies for small g . Therefore it can be found, that $E_0(g_1) < E_0(g_2) < E_0(g_3) < E_0(g_4)$.

Moreover, also the width (σ) increase with decreasing taper parameter, whereas the maximum charge (Q_{\max}) decreases. It can be seen in figure 4.7, that secondary injections occur in the down-ramp region of slow falling densities, leading to a larger energy spread of the beam in these simulations and also an increasing bunch charge can be observed.

It was chosen to determine the bunch charge via integration of the Gaussian fit-function in the 2σ -range. Hence, the particular width of the energy peak in each simulation is taken into account for the computation of Q^{bunch} , allowing an ideal comparison of the absolute amount of accelerated charge.

Statistical errors, such as the influence of the bin width in the histograms or the manual choice of the integration interval, can be prevented with this method. The absolute error of the integration is of the order 10^{-10} and can therefore be neglected. Here, the integration of the Gaussian fit-function in the interval of $[-2\sigma, 2\sigma]$ yields the expected relations:

simulation	1	2	3	4
$\frac{Q^{\text{bunch}}}{pC}$	143.3	143.5	144.9	150.2

Table 4.3: Bunch charge in the main energy peak of each simulation. Similar to the reference simulation, the values were determined with equation 4.8

4.3.2 The Evolution of the Beam Quality

For a convenient analysis of the Courant-Snyder parameters, the down-ramp profile together with the relevant parameter can be seen in each figure on a shared x-axis in 4.6. Furthermore the the density profile without a down-ramp and the respective reference curve are shown in every plot.

Generally, it can be seen that for $y \leq y_{\text{cutoff}}$ the curve of the Courant-Snyder parameters is identical for all simulations. But interesting differences occur after the *cutoff position*, which will be discussed in the following.

Alpha

The parameter alpha, representing the correlation between transverse particle position and slope, is a measure for reaching matching conditions. Electron bunches that are injected via ionisation injection are not matched to the plasma cavity. It has been shown in figure 1.10, that the alpha parameters oscillates around zero, until matching conditions are reached.

In order to keep the amount of written data and the computational cost of the simulations reasonable, the sampling of the alpha parameter cannot represent the actual functional dependency (similar to the reference simulation).

For an adiabatically changing density profile like in simulations 3 and 4, alpha should remain constant if matching conditions were reached. But especially in figure 4.6c and 4.6d the oscillation of the alpha parameter beyond the cutoff position becomes visible. This confirms the observations from 4.2.2, that matching conditions are not reached at y_{cutoff} .

In case of large taper parameters (figure 4.6a and 4.6b) the oscillation of the alpha parameter cannot be seen explicitly. Nevertheless, matching conditions were not reached with these profiles. It is rather seen, that due to the fast decay of the density profile vacuum conditions are quickly realised. The focusing strength decreases accordingly and hence x' remains approximately constant. Thus, alpha becomes kind of an average of the transverse position x , which is not significantly changed in a free drift.

The problem of an unmatched beam is also going to be important for the discussion of the beta and gamma parameter in the following. It will be seen that the adiabatic expansion of an unmatched beam is not necessarily the best solution for an optimisation of the beam quality.

Beta and Gamma

Similar to the discussion for the alpha parameter, the oscillation of the beta and gamma parameter cannot be seen explicitly. But especially in figure 4.6d the oscillation behind the cutoff

(c) Simulation with g_3 .(d) Simulation with g_4 .

Figure 4.6: Courant Snyder parameters $\alpha = -\frac{\langle xx' \rangle}{\epsilon}$, $\beta = \frac{\langle x^2 \rangle}{\epsilon}$ and $\gamma = \frac{\langle x'^2 \rangle}{\epsilon}$ for all down-ramp profiles. The parameters are shown together with the relevant density profile (black) and the parameters of the reference simulation (dotted line) at their respective longitudinal position.

position is observed.

The relation between beta and gamma (Liouville's Theorem) is verified in figure 4.6 also for the down-ramp simulations. The decrease of the beam divergence (gamma) for increasing beam waist (beta) and vice versa is perfectly seen in all plots of the relevant parameters.

Due to the choice of presentation, each down-ramp profile can be compared individually with the reference simulation. For the discussion of the beam development it is interesting to visualise the Courant-Snyder parameters for every iteration, but eventually the beam parameters of the last iteration are compared and summarised in table 4.4.

The intention of applying down-ramps at the end of a plasma channel was, that the beam divergence after the plasma stage can be minimised. Accordingly a minimisation of γ compared with the reference is favourable.

Simulation	α	$\frac{\beta}{mm}$	$\frac{\gamma}{10^{-3}mm^{-1}}$
ref	0.026	590	1.69
1	0.011	1687	0.59
2	-0.025	1326	0.75
3	0.029	718	1.39
4	-0.29	174	6.22

Table 4.4: Courant-Snyder parameters at the end of each PIC simulation.

Despite the unmatched character of the electron bunch, the influence of the down-ramp and an optimisation of the beam quality can be illustrated.

First of all, it can be seen that the beam divergence was not minimised with the fourth setup. In a rough approximation the beam size remained constant and accordingly the gamma parameter has not significantly changed (see figure 4.6d). It is rather observed that the beam matching process continues in the down-ramp territory without truly reaching the desired situation. Especially at $y \approx 3.5$ mm the strong oscillation of all parameters is visible.

In figure 4.7 the total amount of injected charge is visualised together with the density profile of the fourth setup. It can be seen that after the first injection (left edge) secondary injections occur at $z \approx 2.7$ mm and especially at $z \approx 3.5$ mm. These late injections might influence the statistical analysis of the Courant-Snyder parameters on one hand. But also the beam dynamics might be influenced by those electrons, which would additionally delay the arrival at matching conditions.

Figure 4.7: Illustration of the total amount of electrons, that were injected with the fourth density profile. The charge (blue) is visualised in pC on a shared x-axis (representing the longitudinal position in the plasma) together with the density profile (black) of the fourth simulation.

Additionally, also the energy histogram 4.5d indicated that secondary electrons are injected into the cavity during the adiabatic matching. For the fourth simulation these electrons already reach energies in the 100 MeV regime. Hence, the statistical influence of those electrons on the analysis of the Courant-Snyder parameters becomes important, even though an energy filter has been applied. For all the other simulations the influence of these electrons should be negligible

Similar to the fourth simulation, the oscillation of the Courant-Snyder parameters after y_{cutoff} can be seen in simulation 3 as well. It is observed, that the beam waist seems to shrink for approximately 1 mm after the cutoff length up to a longitudinal position $y \approx 3.1$ mm. This might be a consequence of the unmatched beam character.

Afterwards, the adiabatic reduction of the focusing strength causes an expansion of the beam waist, as expected. Compared to the reference simulation, the third profile provides an optimisation of the beam divergence for propagation distances of $y \gtrsim 3.4$ mm.

Contrary to what was expected, a steeper density profile as in figure 4.6a and 4.6b leads to a further reduction of the gamma parameter.

Immediately behind the *cutoff position* both simulations provide a better beam divergence than the super Gaussian profile and reach $\gamma_1 = 0.59 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.75 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ on the scale of this simulation.

Both parameters show slightly non-linear behaviour right behind the cutoff, but after a relatively short propagation distance of $y \gtrsim 0.5 - 1.0$ mm after the cutoff, the focusing force is approximately zero and thus a linear increase of the beam waist is observed.

With regard to the Courant-Snyder parameters it is clearly observed, that within the tested density profiles simulation 1 provides the most favourable beam parameters after the plasma stage. And even though the electron beam was not matched at the end of the plasma plateau at y_{cutoff} , the influence of the down ramp was examined.

Nevertheless, those profiles delivering the best set of Courant-Snyder parameters concurrently provide the lowest bunch energy and -charge. And since the particle acceleration remains a main goal of LWFA a balance between minimising beam divergence and reaching high energies has to be considered, particularly in this special case.

5 Conclusion

The influence of four different density profiles on the bunch energy and charge, as well as the Courant-Snyder parameters was presented. All profiles were compared with the reference profile of super Gaussian shape and their suitability for an optimisation of the beam properties was discussed. And nevertheless the beam has never fulfilled the matching condition at the end of the plasma plateau, it was shown that the choice of the down-ramp profile significantly influences the beam quality.

The kinetic energy and the respective moving angle θ of the accelerated electrons were analysed in a two dimensional histogram and with the help of a Gaussian fit function a further elaboration of the energy distribution was performed. The fit-parameters were then used to define the average bunch energy at the centre of the Gaussian function and via integration of the best fit-function in the 2σ -range the bunch charge Q^{bunch} was quantified.

Afterwards, the time evolution of the Courant-Snyder parameters was discussed and it was observed that the oscillation of the unmatched beam disturbs the adiabatic matching process during the down-ramp transition. Nevertheless it was shown, that on the scale of these LWFA-DIC simulations the beam divergence was optimised with three of four down-ramp profiles.

A summary of all investigated parameters can be found in table 5.1. The comparison of the results always refers to the last iteration of the PIC simulation at a final longitudinal position of $y_{\text{fin}} = 3.93 \text{ mm}$.

Simulation	$\frac{Q^{\text{bunch}}}{\text{pC}}$	$\frac{\langle E \rangle}{\text{MeV}}$	α	$\frac{\beta}{\text{mm}}$	$\frac{\gamma}{10^{-3}\text{mm}^{-1}}$
ref	143.4	208	0.026	590	1.69
$g_1 = 10.0 \text{ mm}^{-1}$	143.3	184	0.011	1687	0.59
$g_2 = 5.0 \text{ mm}^{-1}$	143.5	192	-0.025	1326	0.75
$g_3 = 1.25 \text{ mm}^{-1}$	144.9	255	0.029	718	1.39
$g_4 = 0.625 \text{ mm}^{-1}$	150.2	331	-0.29	174	6.22

Table 5.1: Summary of the results from LWFA-DIC PIC simulations. All parameters refer to the last iteration of the PIC simulation.

Within the down-ramp simulation, the bunch charge and average beam energy continuously increase. While the bunch charge of simulation 1-3 is comparable with the reference simulation, a significantly higher amount of charge is assembled in the main electron bunch at the end of the fourth simulation. A difference $\Delta Q^{\text{bunch}} = |Q_{\text{ref}}^{\text{bunch}} - Q_4^{\text{bunch}}| \approx 6.8 \text{ pC}$ (which is equivalent to approximately 4×10^7 electrons) was observed in this case.

Concerning the average beam energy, a flat plasma-vacuum transition as in simulation 3 and 4 lead to some further acceleration of the electron bunch in the down-ramp region, while the beam energy in simulation 1 and 2 remained relatively low. It was shown, that the acceleration process ends when the plasma density becomes zero. Accordingly, the first simulation, approaching vacuum conditions faster than every other profile, provides the lowest bunch energy.

Contrary to expectations the Courant-Snyder parameters indicate, that the strongest tapering (simulation 1) produces a beam of minimal divergence. The clear decline of the density at y_{cutoff} immediately leads to an increasing beam waist and less beam divergence than the reference simulation. The same qualitative behaviour was found for simulation 2, where a linear vacuum expansion of the beam diameter is observed during the time of simulation.

The third profile does not reach this vacuum conditions on the scale of this simulation, but the expected adiabatic expansion of the beam width while gamma decreases simultaneously was observed. Because of the unmatched beam at the beginning of the down-ramp, the oscillation of the Courant-Snyder parameters continued after y_{cutoff} and the adiabatic expansion of the beam was therefore only observed in the second half of the down-ramp. And even though the gamma parameter actually increased for the first half of the down-ramp, the beam divergence was still optimised at the end of the third simulation.

Particularly in the fourth simulation, the absence of matching conditions at the *cutoff position* had a major influence on the beam expansion process. The oscillation of the Courant-Snyder parameters continued for the whole propagation time and therefore the beam divergence is significantly larger than the reference divergence.

It has been demonstrated with this work, that the beam divergence and the bunch energy cannot be optimised simultaneously with a down-ramp profile. As an ongoing issue of laser-wakefield accelerators, improving the beam divergence always leads to a decrease of the bunch energy.

In case of the given setup, it can be said that the third simulation is the only case, where all the investigated parameters were improved. It provides a great compromise between high bunch energies and charge as well as low beam divergence for the given setup. Out of the investigated cases it is therefore proposed to find an experimental realisation of the third down-ramp profile. But with additional PIC-simulations in the region of g_3 some further optimisation may be found for the proposed setup.

After all, the observations indicated that the choice of the plasma down-ramp certainly has an influence on the beam dynamics after the plasma stage. But nevertheless it was also discovered, that the unmatched character of the beam at the end of the plasma plateau influences the

adiabatic matching process in the vacuum transition.

It was also observed that a flat down-ramp profile is not the optimal solution to minimise the beam divergence of an unmatched beam. The adiabatic beam matching only provides a fine tuning of the beam parameters and reaching matching conditions at the end of the acceleration process should be the next goal for this setup.

With further PIC simulations the influence of other parameters can be tested on the same LWFA setup. In order to reach a matched electron beam at the cutoff position the influence of the laser focus position, shifting the point of injection, can be tested in future computer experiments.

6 Outlook

This work presented the possibility to optimise the beam properties of a plasma accelerated electron bunch, which has been injected into the cavity via ionisation injection.

For the matter of time, only four different density down-ramp profiles have been discussed in this work and a central intention for future studies on this setup is to find an optimal density profile, generating high bunch charges and energies at low divergence. A more refined investigation of the down-ramp profile in the region of the third taper parameter might result in a further optimisation of this setup.

For a conceptual understanding it would also be interesting to extend the plasma in PIC simulation of the third and fourth simulation into areas of low/zero density and compare the results between all simulation at relative longitudinal positions after the plasma stage. This might lead to an improvement of the beam parameters in the fourth case as well, as the end of the adiabatic matching section was not reached in the simulations used for this work.

Furthermore the modelling of a physical realistic down-ramp profile with a smooth cutoff transition can improve the results in future LWFA-DIC simulations.

Nevertheless, for stability reasons the ideal goal in LWFA-DIC experiments and PIC simulations is to find a setup, where the electron beam reaches the matching condition before approaching the down-ramp profile. With the help of PIC simulations this can be tested conveniently for a given setup.

Therefore, it is suggested to find an appropriate sampling for the visualisation of the Courant-Snyder parameters, revealing the oscillation frequency and amplitude of those functions. Hence, the convergence of the alpha parameter can be tracked and the point where $\alpha = 0$ can be determined in computer experiments.

In a close collaboration between LWFA-DIC experiments and PIC simulations a true optimisation of the beam parameters at high energies is foreseeable. Subsequently to this work it is suggested to systematically investigate the influence of other parameters on the electron bunch for a given density profile.

In experiments as well as in PIC simulations the variation of the laser focal position provides an uncomplicated adjustment that influences the point where matching conditions are reached. Additionally it is also considerable to adjust the base density of the plasma, influencing the focusing force as well as the plasma frequency ω_{plasma} and therefore also *dephasing-* and *depletion length*.

If an optimal setup can be found, where the the matching condition is reached before the *cutoff*

position, it would be a next step to repeat the investigation of this work and find an optimal profile for the adiabatic matching of the accelerated electron bunch from plasma to vacuum conditions.

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List of Figures

1.1	Single-Photon-Ionisation	4
1.2	Multi-Photon-Ionisation	4
1.3	Over the barrier ionisation	5
1.4	Linear and non-linear plasma wakes	10
1.5	Three dimensional blowout regime	11
1.6	Blowout regime in two dimensions	12
1.7	Evolution of laser spot size and field strength	13
1.8	Depletion of the driver Laser	17
1.9	Phase Space of an electron bunch	18
1.10	Evolution of Courant-Snyder Parameters	20
2.1	Down-Ramp Profile	23
3.1	PIC-cycle	26
4.1	Density profiles	31
4.2	Histograms for the last interaction of the reference simulation	32
4.3	Energy histograms for the reference simulation	34
4.4	Courant-Snyder parameters reference simulation	35
4.5	Energy histograms of the down-ramp simulations	37
4.6	Courant-Snyder Parameter for the down-ramp simulations	40
4.7	Total charge of the fourth simulation	42

Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich diese Arbeit im Rahmen der Betreuung am Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst habe. Alle Quellen sind als solche gekennzeichnet.

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